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RESIST TO HAVE FUN, HAVE FUN TO EXIST: THE “WILD AMUSEMENTS” OF BLACK PEOPLE IN SALVADOR (BA) AT THE TURN OF THE CENTURY (1890-1910)

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ABSTRACT

I discuss the entertainment of black people in Salvador from the 19th to the 20th century (from 1890 to 1910). The main objective of the dissertation is to analyze, discuss and infer about the problematizations of how the black population entertained itself in a markedly black society, which was undergoing political changes (transition from monarchy to republic), social changes (end of slavery through legal frameworks) and cultural changes (attempts to “civilize” people through the prohibition and/or repression of some customs). I used newspapers from the period as my main sources, in addition to the legislation of the period, traveler’s reports and the like. After delving into the sources, I defined the entertainment to be investigated, which were Samba, Batuque, Candomblé, the Bonfim Festivals and Forbidden Games. The theoretical framework was presented in a fluid manner throughout the text, and the analysis of the sources indicated here followed a spiral pattern.